

FILAMENT WINDING: ANALYTICAL KINEMATIC SOLUTIONS FOR LATHE-CONFIGURED WINDING MACHINES

S. Koussios, O.K. Bergsma and A. Beukers

*Design and Production of Composite Structures, Faculty of Aerospace Engineering
Delft University of Technology
Kluyverweg 1 P.O. Box 058, 2600 GB, Delft, The Netherlands*

SUMMARY: In this paper we propose and evaluate a simple method for the derivation of the machine motions for filament winding applications. To obtain entirely analytical solutions, a reduction has been realised towards lathe-configured winding machines while exclusively considering shells of revolution. The proposed method has been applied on an extensive range of rotationally symmetric objects through simulations and experiments on a four-axes winding machine. It is believed that the provided equations can be of great use for rapid prototyping purposes since they set the ability for creating the required CNC machine control data by means of simple programs.

KEYWORDS: Filament winding, Lathe winder, Kinematics, Machine motion

INTRODUCTION

The process of filament winding can generally be characterised by improved fibre placement accuracy, high fibre volume ratios, and constant quality [8, 9, 10]. Therefore this technique is usually involved in the manufacturing process of high-specification products like rocket engine cases and high-performance pressure vessels [2].

The design stage for filament winding products does roughly consist of three stages: mandrel shape determination, creation of suitable winding patterns, and evaluation of the kinematic aspects [7, 9]. The latter consists of the selection of a proper machine configuration followed by the determination of the required motions this machine has to perform. Assuming the most common machine geometry (lathe winder) we focus here on the evaluation of the associated kinematic equations. Unless the designer has access to filament winding simulation software, the solution of the kinematic equations is usually a time consuming issue.

In this paper we provide an entirely analytical solution for the solution of the kinematic equations, sufficiently tailored for evaluation with the aid of simple programs like spreadsheets. It should be noted however, that two important assumptions took here place: the machine geometry is a lathe winder with a zero feed eye elevation, and the treated mandrel is rotationally symmetric. With the outline of a generic kinematic model in the first section, we proceed to the lathe winder configuration in the next section where we realise a reduction for the corresponding system of equations. Emphasis has been given to the proper determination

of the spindle rotation and the exact solution for the feed eye inclination. With the obtained methodologies and analytical expressions, we finally present some results and asses the usability of the equations provided here.

GENERIC KINEMATIC MODEL

Machine geometry

Let a three-dimensional body (referred to as mandrel) be attached to a generic filament winding machine configuration, figure 1. The feed eye is assumed to perform three simultaneous translations $\{X, Y, Z\}$ and the mandrel itself is rotating around three orthogonal axes [5]. The rotation sequence is $\{Q, \gamma, R\}$. Additional features are (figure 1) the feed eye situated at $\mathbf{p} = \{X, Y, Z\} \cdot \{E_0\}$, the position where the roving enters the resin bath unit $\mathbf{q} = \{x, y, z\} \cdot \{E_0\}$, and the locus where the roving leaves the spool $\mathbf{r} = \{r_x, r_y, r_z\} \cdot \{E_0\}$. In addition, several distances associated with the roving (as it proceeds from spool to mandrel) are given by Greek symbols (figure 1).

At the centre of gravity of the mandrel, a right-handed reference system $\{E_3\}$ (figure 2) and an inertia reference system $\{E_0\}$ are attached. The orientation of $\{E_3\}$ can be related to $\{E_0\}$ with the aid of three consequent Euler rotations over respectively the angles Q, γ and R [3]. The body under consideration is subjected to:

- Body rotation Q of $\{E_0\}$ with respect to the \mathbf{j}_0 axis: the resulting coordinate system is $\{E_1\}$.
- Body rotation γ of $\{E_1\}$ with respect to the \mathbf{i}_1 axis: the resulting coordinate system is $\{E_2\}$.
- Body rotation R of $\{E_2\}$ with respect to the \mathbf{k}_2 axis: the resulting coordinate system is $\{E_3\}$. The latter forms the basis for the body-related vector quantities.

Fig. 1: Schematic view of the generic winding machine

Fig. 2: The three Euler rotation describing the orientation of the mandrel with respect to $\{E_0\}$

The rotations can be expressed as follows [3, 5]:

$$\begin{aligned} \{E_1\} &= [R_{10}] \cdot \{E_0\} \\ \{E_2\} &= [R_{21}] \cdot \{E_1\} \\ \{E_3\} &= [R_{32}] \cdot \{E_2\} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $[R_{ij}]$ are orthogonal transformation matrices, equation (2):

$$[R_{10}] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos Q & 0 & -\sin Q \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \sin Q & 0 & \cos Q \end{bmatrix}, \quad [R_{21}] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \gamma & \sin \gamma \\ 0 & -\sin \gamma & \cos \gamma \end{bmatrix}, \quad [R_{32}] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos R & \sin R & 0 \\ -\sin R & \cos R & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Notice that the feed eye and the spool are not subjected to any rotation; their position vectors are referred to the inertia system $\{E_0\}$. The body related reference system $\{E_3\}$ can directly be expressed in the inertia one $\{E_0\}$ [3, 5]:

$$\{E_3\} = [R_{32}] \cdot [R_{21}] \cdot [R_{10}] \cdot \{E_0\} = [R_{tot}] \cdot \{E_0\} \quad (3)$$

where:

$$[R_{tot}] = \begin{bmatrix} cQcR + sQs\gamma sR & -cQsR + sQs\gamma cR & sQc\gamma \\ c\gamma sR & c\gamma cR & -s\gamma \\ -sQcR + cQs\gamma sR & sQsR + cQs\gamma cR & cQc\gamma \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

with $c\# = \cos\#$ and $s\# = \sin\#$. Returning to body under consideration (figure 1), the position of a locus (i, j) belonging to the fibre path is given by a vector \mathbf{G} that is defined in $\{E_3\}$. The fibre path orientation at that point is given by the unity vector $\Delta\mathbf{G}$ (that is also defined in $\{E_3\}$, figure 3).

Fig. 3: Position and orientation vector of the fibre path on the mandrel

The line connecting the delivery eye with the contact locus of the fibre on the surface of the wound object is referred as “free hanging fibre”. The metric distance of the latter is indicated by λ . Notice that $\Delta \mathbf{G}$ is a unity vector. From figures 1 and 3 it follows immediately that [5]:

$$\mathbf{G} \cdot \{E_3\} + \lambda \Delta \mathbf{G} \cdot \{E_3\} = \mathbf{p} \cdot \{E_0\} \quad (5)$$

Although the decision to describe the involved vectors in $\{E_0\}$ or $\{E_3\}$ is free, we choose here $\{E_0\}$. With equation (3) we obtain the following expression:

$$\mathbf{G}[R_{tot}] \cdot \{E_0\} + \lambda \Delta \mathbf{G} \cdot [R_{tot}] \cdot \{E_0\} = \mathbf{p} \cdot \{E_0\} \quad (6)$$

Fibre path parameters

The fibre locus under consideration is denoted by the index combination (i, j) where i stands for the i^{th} point belonging to the j^{th} circuit (winding), figure 3. The vector \mathbf{G} describing the position of the locus (i, j) on the body with respect to $\{E_3\}$ is given by [4]:

$$\mathbf{G}(i, j) = \begin{Bmatrix} g(\theta_i) \sin \theta_i \cos \phi(i, j) \\ g(\theta_i) \sin \theta_i \sin \phi(i, j) \\ g(\theta_i) \cos \theta_i \end{Bmatrix}^T \cdot \{E_3\} \quad (7)$$

For the orientation vector $\Delta \mathbf{G}$ we obtain [4]:

$$\Delta \mathbf{G}(i, j) = \begin{Bmatrix} \cos \alpha(i) \sin \beta(i) \cos \phi(i, j) - \sin \alpha(i) \sin \phi(i, j) \\ \cos \alpha(i) \sin \beta(i) \sin \phi(i, j) + \sin \alpha(i) \cos \phi(i, j) \\ \cos \alpha(i) \cos \beta(i) \end{Bmatrix}^T \cdot \{E_3\} \quad (8)$$

We assume now that the feed eye \mathbf{p} is placed on the $\{x_0, y_0\}$ plane, hence $Z = 0$. According to figure 1, the total roving length is given by:

$$S(i, j) = L(i, j) + \lambda(i, j) + \sigma(i, j) + \delta \quad (9)$$

where $L(i, j)$ is the roving length wound on the mandrel, and:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{(r_x - X)^2 + (r_y - Y)^2} \quad (10)$$

One should notice that the distance δ remains constant since it is entirely determined by the feed eye structure.

Winding equation

For the solution of equation (6) we introduce now the following vectors [5]:

$$\mathbf{v}_1 = \begin{Bmatrix} v_{11} \\ v_{12} \\ v_{13} \end{Bmatrix} = [R_{tot}] \cdot \mathbf{G}^T = [R_{tot}] \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} G_x \\ G_y \\ G_z \end{Bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{v}_2 = \begin{Bmatrix} v_{21} \\ v_{22} \\ v_{23} \end{Bmatrix} = [R_{tot}] \cdot \Delta \mathbf{G}^T = [R_{tot}] \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta G_x \\ \Delta G_y \\ \Delta G_z \end{Bmatrix}$$

The winding equation (6) becomes:

$$\mathbf{v}_1 - \mathbf{p}^T + \lambda \mathbf{v}_2 = \mathbf{0}^T \quad (12)$$

Expressing this in matrix form gives:

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{11} & -p_x & v_{21} \\ v_{12} & -p_y & v_{22} \\ v_{13} & -p_z & v_{23} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ \lambda \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{M} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ \lambda \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

This homogeneous linear system of equations involves the following unknowns:

- Row(1): Q, γ, R, X, λ
- Row(2): γ, R, Y, λ
- Row(3): Q, γ, R, Z, λ

The first and third row of \mathbf{M} involve similar unknowns; hence, the following reduced matrix can be constructed:

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{11} - p_x & v_{21} \\ v_{13} - p_z & v_{23} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ \lambda \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{N} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ \lambda \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

The system presented here as a non-trivial solution if:

$$\det \mathbf{N} = 0 \quad (15)$$

Fig. 4: The lathe winder configuration as deduced from figure 1

LATHE WINDER CONFIGURATION

General solution

The lathe winder configuration is represented by: $\gamma = -\pi/2$ and $Z = 0$, (figures 1 and 4) [6]. For simplicity we assume here a polar coordinate system for the body and we temporarily neglect the counter combination (i, j) . With $C = Q + R$, the system of kinematic equations (6) becomes:

$$\begin{cases} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{cases} = \begin{cases} \rho \cos(C + \phi) - \lambda[\sin \alpha \sin(C + \phi) - \cos \alpha \sin \beta \cos(C + \phi)] \\ z + \lambda \cos \alpha \cos \beta \\ -\rho \sin(C + \phi) - \lambda[\sin \alpha \cos(C + \phi) + \cos \alpha \sin \beta \sin(C + \phi)] \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

with $Z = 0$. The determinant of \mathbf{N} (equation (14)) is given by:

$$-\rho \sin \alpha + X[\sin \alpha \cos(C + \phi) + \cos \alpha \sin \beta \sin(C + \phi)] = 0 \quad (17)$$

The following parameters are now introduced:

$$\begin{aligned} \omega &= C + \phi \quad (= Q + R + \phi) \\ \eta &= [\sin \alpha \cos \omega + \cos \alpha \sin \beta \sin \omega] \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Notice that η is the same as v_{23} , which is provided by the combination of equations (8) and (11b). With the third row of equation (16) and the determinant (17), the following system can be constructed:

$$-\begin{Bmatrix} \det[N] \\ Z \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \rho \sin \alpha - X\eta \\ \rho \sin \omega + \lambda \eta \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

The combination of (19) and the second row of (16) leads to the following expressions for the machine motions:

$$C = -\phi \pm \arcsin \left(\frac{\lambda \sin \alpha}{\sqrt{\lambda^2 \sin^2 \alpha + (\rho + \lambda \cos \alpha \sin \beta)^2}} \right)$$

$$X = \sqrt{\lambda^2 \sin^2 \alpha + (\rho + \lambda \cos \alpha \sin \beta)^2} \quad (20)$$

$$Y = \rho + \lambda \cos \alpha \cos \beta$$

Spindle rotation

The evaluation of the spindle rotation C involves an inverse trigonometric function. The proper sign for the angular argument of this function can be determined as follows: in equation (19) the term $\rho \sin \alpha$ is always positive since we assume a positive ϕ -propagation (figure 3). In particular for the case of geodesic winding, this term will become equal to the radius of the polar opening of the mandrel [5]. Since $X > 0$, the parameter η is positive (first row of equation (19)). In addition, since $\lambda \geq 0$ and $\rho > 0$ (second row of (19)), the argument ω must belong to the interval $(-\pi/2, \pi/2)$. This conclusion however, does still not completely determine the argument, so an additional condition is here required. The third row of equation (16) gives (with $\omega = C + \phi$, equation (18)):

$$\cos \omega = -\left(\frac{\sin \omega}{\lambda \sin \alpha} \right) (\rho + \lambda \cos \alpha \sin \beta) = K (\rho + \lambda \cos \alpha \sin \beta) \quad (21)$$

$$\Rightarrow \operatorname{sgn}(\cos \omega) = \operatorname{sgn}(\rho + \lambda \cos \alpha \sin \beta) = \operatorname{sgn}(\Xi)$$

where K is a positive real number and “sgn” stands for sign. With this information, the proper expression for the determination of C (in radians) becomes:

$$C = -\phi - \operatorname{sgn}(\Xi) \left[\arcsin \left(\frac{\lambda \sin \alpha}{\sqrt{\lambda^2 \sin^2 \alpha + (\rho + \lambda \cos \alpha \sin \beta)^2}} \right) \right] + \left(\frac{\operatorname{sgn}(\Xi) - 1}{2} \right) \pi \quad (22)$$

The complete set of primary machine movements is now determined. It consists of equations (20b), (20c) and (22).

Feed eye rotation

A secondary movement but of great importance is the feed eye rotation A , see figure 5. This rotation must guarantee twist-free roving placement, as it is directed from the feed eye to the mandrel. Especially for broad tapes, this requirement is of major importance. From figure 5 and equations (8) and (11b) we can immediately derive:

Fig. 5: Determination of the feed eye rotation

$$A = \arctan\left(\frac{v_{22}}{v_{23}}\right) = \arctan\left(\frac{\cos \alpha \cos \beta}{\eta}\right) \quad (23)$$

where η is given in (18). Accordingly, the complete set of obtained values for S , C , A , X and Y depends on the fibre locus (i, j) and λ .

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The proposed method has been evaluated on an extensive range of rotationally symmetrical shapes while significantly varying the distance λ . The reason for this variation is that λ is the main control parameter for the determination of the spindle rotation C . More specific, with a given mandrel radius ρ , winding angle α and meridian slope β (figure 3), the sign of Ξ is entirely controlled by λ (equation (21)). Furthermore, the generated machine coordinates have been evaluated on a filament-winding machine by means of running CNC control data generated with these expressions on a BAER filament winding machine [1]. Although the solution can be evaluated on a direct way, we provide here some examples referring to typical cases like a feed eye that contacts the mandrel and the winding process of an oblate spheroid with flat polar areas (this shape provides considerable freedom to vary the λ values).

Feed eye contacting the mandrel

For $\lambda = 0$, we obtain with the aid of equation (20), (22) and (23):

$$\begin{aligned} C &= -\phi \\ A &= \arctan\left(\frac{\cos \beta}{\tan \alpha}\right) \\ X &= \rho \\ Y &= z \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

which are the coordinates of a the roving itself, referred to the mandrel coordinate system $\{E_3\}$, figures 1 and 3.

Fig. 6: Frames from the simulation of winding an oblate spheroid with flat polar areas on a lathe winder

Oblate spheroid with flat polar areas

In figure 6 we provide several frames of a simulation carried out. The winding angle at the equator of the treated mandrel is rather small (8°) and the flat polar areas force the feed eye inclination to perform a rigorous transition from $+90^\circ$ to -90° .

CONCLUSIONS

In regard to filament winding on a lathe-configured machine, in this paper we have presented a method for the determination of the required machine motions on an entirely analytical way. Beginning with the derivation of the generic winding equations, a reduction towards the lathe winder has been realised. Assuming rotational symmetry the entire set of required motions has been obtained where a decision function Ξ is introduced for the proper determination of the spindle rotation. In addition, the analytical solution for the feed eye rotation A is here outlined. The obtained solutions have been verified by means of simulation and experiments on a BAER 4-axes filament winding machine, available at the constructions and materials laboratory at the faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Delft University of Technology

The added value of the proposed solution is its straight forwardness and suitability for direct evaluation. However, since the geometrical problem of placing a fibre on a prescribed path is over-determined (3 equations with 4 unknowns), a decision has to be taken regarding the magnitude of a particular degree of freedom. The common solution to this problem is the introduction of some restrictions on the cross carriage translation X (that usually is set to follow an enlarged mandrel contour) or, equivalently, by preserving a constant distance λ .

In this model, since the entire set of machine motions is formulated as a collection of functions co-depending on the same parameter λ , the setting up of an optimisation problem for minimising the production time is believed to be an easy task. In addition, for rapid prototyping purposes, the proposed solutions can directly be generated by simple programs.

As an extension to rotationally symmetric objects, a direct solver for the kinematics of arbitrary-shaped mandrels is currently under preparation.

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